

Teachers With Ancillary Function: School Property Custodian in Focus Division of Agusan Del Sur

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Abstract. This study examined and investigated the experiences, coping mechanisms, and educational insights learned from the experiences of teachers assigned as school property custodians. Qualitative approach to research phenomenological from 8 teachers assigned as school property custodians from the different schools in Prosperidad III district on the experiences of teachers as property custodians were observed: time pressure, heavy workload, stress, and perseverance. Teachers assigned as school property custodians' coping mechanisms for the challenges encountered were as follows: motivating one another, optimism and positivity, having a work-life balance, and good planning and time management. Through their experiences and coping mechanisms, we generated new knowledge and ideas on the challenges the teachers assigned as school property custodians encountered. Finally, the insights gained from the experiences of teachers being the school property custodians were keeping a positive attitude, being flexible, health consideration, and commitment and dedication. These themes can be described as an input in the successful crafting and conduct of training for teachers to capacitate them on the different strategies and techniques in ensuring the learning continuity of students during a pandemic.

KEY WORDS

1. Teachers as school property custodian
2. coping mechanisms
3. educational management insights

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1. Introduction

Ancillary functions are defined as engagements that provide vital support to the primary activities or operation of an organization and system. The ancillary functions among teachers are operationally defined as that aside from being classroom teachers, they have other school-related functions, such as being designated as grade-level advisers, subject coordinators/chairs, club moderators, sports coaches, in-charge of co-curricular and extracurricular activities, and community involvement services. The

Department of Education categorizes classroom teachers into two categories: teachers without ancillary responsibilities and teachers with ancillary responsibilities. This means that in addition to being classroom teachers, they have other classroom-related functions. Some of them are designated as Grade-Level Coordinators, Club Moderators, Clinic In-Charge, School Statisticians, and Canteen Managers, among others. Ancillary responsibilities of teachers often lead to losing their motivation, satisfaction, and com-

petence, and even feeling burned out (Howard Johnson, 2004). In the study conducted by Parham and Gordon (2011), a person seeks for multiple ancillary functions only because of promotion. Furthermore, scholars have questioned the nature and characteristics of teachers with ancillary responsibilities. Zickar, Gibby, and Jenny (2004) reported that an employee is more likely to encounter professional rivalry because you have to exert more effort to manage multiple roles and behaviors to multiple ancillary responsibilities. In the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) schools are facing issues on meeting the critical factors that are significant in enhancing quality education. Variables, such as overlapping tasks and co-curricular activities of teachers, are reported as factors that hinder quality education in the country, as cited by (Jackson, Schwab, Schuler, 1986). In Mindanao, the study of Retubada (2004) mentioned that multiple ancillary functions of teachers are one of the problems encountered by schools in Davao Del Sur, Region XI. He cited that teachers, while performing their main function as classroom advisers, are also given extra non-teaching functions called ancillary responsibilities as their additional workload since there is a need to assign these teachers as subject area coordinators, grade level heads, canteen managers, sports coordinator, SBM, coordinator, club moderators, cluster subject area coordinator, coaches in different contests in cluster, division, regional and even at national levels which resulted into poor performance of teachers as well as students. However, in the study of Parham and Gordon (2011), combining multiple ancillary functions emphasized positive impacts on an individual's well-being. Canadian teachers with multiple ancillary functions are reported to be less worn-out, stress-free, have high performance in their jobs, and with lower intentions to quit (Yahya, Ismail, Salleh, Abdulah, 2015). In other countries, like in Indonesia, ancillary services are embedded in the schools to support the implementation of the first four national standards of education regarding the national goal of education. In the Philippine context, these ancillary functions are provided according to the expertise of the teachers. However, it could not be avoided that these functions are also given to teachers upon entry, as experienced teachers have the confidence to decline when these functions are given to them. In other instances, these functions are given to those who have lesser teaching loads, regardless if they have the expertise or not (Salisi et.al. 2021). According to Tomacruz (2019), public school teachers' workload is limited to teaching and other non-teaching tasks. Given this workload, actual teaching is increasingly being sidelined by the multitude of other responsibilities and roles that teachers play. The Magna Carta for Public School Teachers requires teachers to devote 6 hours to daily teaching. On top of this, teachers are often tasked with administrative work, including paperwork, training and seminars, and tasks related to budget, disaster response, and health, among others. Aside from these, the study said teachers were likewise expected to participate in various government programs, such as mass immunization activities, conditional cash transfers, feeding programs, population census-taking, anti-illegal drug efforts, and elections, to name a few. In the local scenario, particularly in Prosperidad District, Division of Agusan del Sur, the property custodian was fully loaded with paperwork, which more often affects their main function: teaching and handling a class inside the classroom. It is in this premise that this study was conceptualized to find out the experiences of teachers performing as school property custodians within the district and know about their good practices in performing as such.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The goal of the study was to explore the realities on the experiences of teachers in performing as school property custodian. This study was beneficial for administrators, as data gathered served as research-based information that will be of use in motivating and giving technical assistance to teachers in innovating the methodologies applicable in the context of the school in performing as school property custodian.

1.2. Research Questions—The primary research questions of this study are the following:

- (1) What are the experiences of teachers in performing as school property custodians?
- (2) How do the teachers cope on the challenges in performing as school property custodians?
- (3) What educational management insights were gained from the experiences of the informants?

1.3. Definition of Terms—The following terms were operationally defined to make this study more comprehensive. Ancillary functions. Some of the ancillary functions that are being designated to teachers are subject coordinators, grade-level chairpersons, organizations/ club moderators, school paper advisers, coaches in academic and non-academic contests, canteen managers, and members of various technical and working committees. Teacher property custodian. The designated Property Custodians perform, among others, important workloads that include the receipt, issuance, and maintenance, safekeeping of supplies, materials and equipment and other properties and facilities of the school.

1.4. Significant of the Study—This study would be significant to the following person in the educational field: For Policy Makers. The findings of this study would help them in the effective implementation of educational management practices for the teachers in performing as school property custodians. For Administrators. The findings of this study would provide technical assistance to teachers in adapting best practices in performing as school property custodians. For Teachers. The findings of this study would equip teachers with the realization to continue to attend professional development activities in order to acquire a new set of skills required in performing as a school property custodian

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This research is anchored on the theory of Job enlargement (Buhler, 1990). He said that Job enlargement can be defined as utilization of “horizontal” skills, or ancillary functions which require skills that are at a similar level of complexity and responsibility. In teaching, it may consist of creating additional work load aside from the regular task given (Firestone, 1991). Research on the off shot of job enlargement programs shows that motivation is increased when additional tasks are interdependent (Wong Campion, 1991). It was also added that job enlargement is directly related to high satisfaction (Campion McClelland, 1993). Research shows that job enlargement has a positive effect on teachers’ instructions since it became more diversified (Firestone, 1991). In another study, conducted by Conley and Levinson (1993), they said that teachers’ multiple ancillary functions, such as teaching and non-teaching responsibilities, improved teachers’ skills. Another theory used in this study is Job Enlargement, Job Expansion, and Job Enrichment Theories by Herzberg, F. (1968). The three theories are extensions of the Herzberg Motivation Theory. Job enlargement is a technique of job design that adds to job tasks and responsibilities. Its objective is to increase

job satisfaction by reducing a job's monotony. Job enrichment is a management concept involving redesigning jobs to make them more challenging for the employee and less repetitive work. Job expansion means the horizontal expansion of a job. It consists of adding tasks at the same skill and responsibility level. It is done to avoid getting bored by workers (Tare, 2016). Another theory used in this study is the Role Theory by Robert Merton in 1957. Role theory has its origin in the work of the American sociologist Robert Merton (Merton, 1957). Roles refer to people's social position (e.g., teacher, mother, and customer) and behavior associated with that position. Roles tend to carry certain risks and benefits which may vary by individual characteristics, historical time, and cultural context. Roles can provide connection to other people and access to resources, which in turn may promote feelings of security, status enhancement, and ego gratification. Roles also provide directions for behavior in otherwise uncertain situations (Hogg, 2000), which may serve to reduce stress and improve well-being. People often fulfill a set of roles at the same time (e.g., mother, director, and child), and this set may change over the life course (Riley and Riley, 1994; Rotolo, 2000). With aging an increasing imbalance occurs between the number of roles gained and lost (Baltes, 1997). Older people tend to lose more roles than they gain, such as parent, spouse, worker, and active member of society. Volunteering and helping others can

substitute for roles lost over the life course. For example, becoming a volunteer after retirement may alleviate any negative consequences associated with losing the worker role, such as a loss of a sense of personal value and identity (Greenfield and Marks, 2004). The ancillary functions among the teachers are operationally defined as that aside from their being classroom teachers, they have other school-related functions, such as being designated as grade level advisers, subject coordinators/chairs, club moderators, coaches in sports, in-charge in co-curricular and property custodians. The conceptual framework of the study is presented in Figure 1. Based on the figure, there are two interconnected variables. These variables are the experiences of teachers in performing as school property custodians; (2) Coping mechanisms of teachers on the challenges encountered in performing as school property custodians; (3) educational management insights gained from the informants' experiences. Moreover, ancillary functions are defined as engagements that provide vital support to the primary activities or operation of an organization and system. The ancillary functions among the teachers are operationally defined as that aside from their being classroom teachers, they have other school-related functions, such as being designated as grade level advisers, subject coordinators/chairs, club moderators, coaches in sports, in-charge in co-curricular and extracurricular activities and community involvement services.

2. Methodology

This chapter presents the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. Exploring facts and knowledge in this study necessitates the consequent design and implementation, as elaborated in this chapter. The three most common qualitative methods are participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method was particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation was appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) was optimal for collecting data on individuals' personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when exploring sensitive topics.

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

Focus groups effectively elicit data on a group’s cultural norms and generate broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. Patton (2002) defined phenomenology as an inquiry that asks the question, “What is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people?” “the goal of this research worked well with this definition in trying to understand the experiences of teachers as they perform their additional task as school property. Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to be prepared for an investigation greater in depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested information be viewed as only the tip of the iceberg.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption is a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret data in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used to reach conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. Good research begins with the selection of the topic, problem, or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Stanage (1987) traces ‘paradigm’ back to its Greek (paradigma) and Latin origins (paradigma), meaning pattern, model, or example among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions are taken. Differently stated, a paradigm was an action of

submitting to a view. This view was supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2000) who defend a research paradigm a “basic set of belief that guide action”, dealing with first principles, “ultimates’ or the researcher’s worldview or philosophy. Ontology. This part of the research pertains on how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012), reality is subjective and multiple as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the

reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, experiences of teachers in performing as school property custodian are discussed by the participants and tries to look into their strategies in addressing the challenges and educational insights. In this study, the researcher relied on voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The participant's answers to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. The responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progressed. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln as cited by Creswell (2012) state that on the epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen the distance between himself or herself from the participants. He suggests that being a researcher he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an 'insider'. Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2011). Researcher identified phenomenology with the use of thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers "hold explicit belief". This study intended to gather information from the participants or teachers in Prosperidad Dis-

trict as to how they perform their function as school property custodian based on the guidelines set by DepEd and the Inter Agency Task Force (IATF). It is assured that close interaction with the participants was established to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry, particularly on teachers' experiences and strategies for performing as school property custodians. Axiology. It refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2012) avers that the role of values in a study was significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes their interpretation in conjunction with the interpretation of participants. The researcher ensured the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understands the personal and value-laden nature of information gathered from the study. Therefore, the researcher preserved the merit of the participants' answers and carefully interpreted the answers in the light of the participants' interpretation. Rhetoric. It means reporting what reality was through the eyes of the research participants. This was important because it meant that the researcher would report objectively what was observed and heard from the participants. The research used personal voice and qualitative terms and limited definitions. In the context of the study, the researcher used the first person to elucidate the experiences of teachers as they perform their tasks as school property custodians.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—The methodology was different from the method. Methodology is a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study, the experiences of elementary

school teachers as school property custodians in Prosperidad District were gathered through an In-Depth Interview (IDI), and their coping mechanisms were extracted from the participants. The researcher's drive in knowing the deeper meaning of the experiences of elementary school teachers in performing as school

property custodian became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means of which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited from Gerodias, (2013) considered helpful in looking for “meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences and phenomena”. By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the experiences elementary school teachers in performing their ancillary function in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols and meaning of the experiences presented. Phenomenological research was based on two premises. The first was that experience was a valid, rich and rewarding source of knowledge. According to Becker (1992), as cited in Morrissey Higgs, (2006), that experience was a source of knowledge and shapes one’s behavior. From the

definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge and that we can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By doing phenomenology, which concerns the “what” and the “how” (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher projected that the experiences and mechanisms used by the elementary school teachers were explored and insights drawn, which would form the basis for possible future research and policy analysis about this research.

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—This study employed a qualitative approach to research specifically a phenomenological research design. According to Creswell, (2012), phenomenology was an approach to qualitative research that focused on the commonality of lived experiences within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach was to arrive at a description of the nature of the particular phenomenon. Typically, interviews were conducted with individuals with first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, were also used. The data were read and reread and was culled for phrases and themes grouped into clusters of meanings. Through this process, the researcher constructed the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. Moreover, Maxwell (2013) also added that phenomenology, with its roots in philosophy, psychology, and education, attempts to extract the purest, untainted data. In some interpretations of the approach, the re-

searcher uses bracketing to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or her from the process. One method of bracketing is taking notes. According to Corbetta (2003), the phenomenological research design was a qualitative type of research for which interviews provide in-depth method that can grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and help grasp the subjects’ perspective. Creswell, (2012) also claimed that interviews were primarily done in qualitative research and occur when researchers ask one or more participants general, open-ended questions and record their answers. Often audio tapes were utilized to allow more consistent transcription. Interviews also useful to follow-up with individual respondents after questionnaires, such as to further investigate their responses. In qualitative research, interviews were used to pursue the meanings of central themes in the world of their subjects. The main task in doing interviews was to understand the meaning of what the interviewees say (McNamara, 1999). Withal, based on the statements of Quad (2016), the

researcher transcribed and typed the data into a computer file in order to analyze it after interviewing. Interviews particularly be useful for uncovering the story behind a participant's experiences and pursuing in-depth information about a topic. The researcher collected data from individuals who have experienced the phenomenon under investigation, typically via long interviews. Next, the data analysis involved triangulation that extracted significant statements from the transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each statement fell under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied up together to make a general description of the experience both the textural description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it was experienced. The researcher incorporated his or her personal meaning of the experiences here. Finally, the report was written such that readers understand better the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed out. The re-

searcher required a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects that were selected into the study were individuals who have actually experienced the phenomenon. The researcher needed to bracket his or her own experiences and observations, which was difficult to do. The researcher also needed to decide as to how and when his or her personal observations be incorporated into the study. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches was based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity, and emphasize the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such they were powerful tools for understanding subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the cluster of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Since the focus of this study was to explore and assess the teacher experience and feelings towards the school environment and the perspectives of seasoned teachers, the researcher intends to employ the phenomenology type of qualitative method research.

2.4. Research Participants—The participants of this study were Eight (8) elementary school teachers assigned as property custodians from Prosperidad District, Agusan del Sur. The participants were chosen based on the following criteria: (1) must be in the service for at least five years; (2) elementary school teacher; and

(3) teacher property custodian. The researcher utilized the purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2014). It is also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic (Marshall, 1996).

2.5. Ethical Considerations—The ethical considerations were significant in the design of this research study. The researcher needed to consider several ethical issues about the research participant in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations can be specified as one of the most important parts of the research. The researcher

needs to adhere to promote the aims of the research imparting authentic knowledge, truth and prevention of error. Social Value. The research was essential to society. In this study, the social value was focused on the experience of teachers. This study was conducted explicitly among the elementary teachers. This study also served as

a basis for the higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions from which classroom teachers could benefit. Thus, the social problem that pushes the researcher's interest is the challenges the teachers face in using interactive media instruction in the classroom as a way to ameliorate teaching competence. Informed Consent. In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of Participation, as cited by McLeod (2009), was adhered to. The invitation to the participants ensured that their participation in the research was completely voluntary and based on understanding adequate information. The recruitment and selection of participants were lodged in the appendices of this study. Gaining the trust and support of research participants was critical to informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Walker, 2007, as cited by Pillerin, 2012). All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a signed personal acknowledgment, consent, and an indication of a willingness to participate in the study release. The purpose of the informed consent letter was to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the study's intent, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and anticipate the information the informants were expected to provide. All participants were required to sign and return the consent letter to the researcher before participating. Vulnerability of Research Participants. This study's participants could answer the research instrument, for they are all professional teachers in public elementary schools. Thus, the researcher assured them that as the researcher, he or she can easily be reached through the contact number and address in case there are some clarifications or questions about the study. Risks, Benefits, and Safety. The recruitment of the respondents was free of coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Moreover, respon-

dents were provided with the contact numbers of the panel chair or panel members in case they had queries related to the study. Furthermore, in the event that respondents would experience potential discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelling to participate in any manner. Further, the researcher ensured that the respondents were safe during the survey and interview. Thus, the questionnaire was distributed in a safe venue and administered at a convenient time. The dominant concern of this study was the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality and the minimization of risk. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent to this was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the data cannot be traced back to their real sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure the anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed output that was carried out from this study was kept in anonymity. Furthermore, all the issues were considered so that there were no conflicts of interest between the researcher and the respondents. Any misleading information and representation of primary data findings in a biased way must be avoided. Justice. The respondents were informed of the researcher's role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were briefed that they had to be fully honest in answering the survey questions and that any communication-related to the research should be done with honesty. Similarly, they were informed that they were the ones to benefit first from the study's results. Transparency. The respondents accessed the results of the study and heads of the participating schools because the information was available and would be

placed on a CD or other storage devices, which can be requested from the researcher. In addition, by learning about the study's results, classroom teachers would be aware of the significance of the study and its contribution to their well-being. Further, each of the participants was advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process and that they can be requested and allowed to verify their transcript after the interview is carried out. This allowed the participants to amend or remove any information they felt might identify them. The researcher reserved the right to use pseudonyms and change names and/or non-significant dates in the interest of protecting the participant's identity in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that he or she possesses the needed qualifications to conduct the study. The researcher should be completing the academic requirements, passed the comprehensive examination prior to thesis writing which was the last requirement to obtain the masteral degree, and that the researcher should be qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study would reach its completion. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher strived that

the study can be completed successfully on the specified time and that he or she was equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee helped enhance the paper by giving the needed suggestions and recommendations for improving the study. Also, the researcher ensured that he or she has enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, it was hoped that this study would be completed within the target time. Community Involvement. The researcher showed respect to the local tradition, culture and views of the respondents in this study. Moreover, this study did not involve any use of deceit in any stage of its implementation, and specifically, in the recruitment of the participants, or methods of data collection. Furthermore, the researcher necessarily expressed great pleasure for the wholehearted participation of the interviewees in the conduct of the study. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher. The researcher respected other works by properly citing the author and rewriting what someone else has said his or her way. The researcher also used quotes to indicate that the text had been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher assured that honesty was present in working on the manuscript and no intentional misrepresentation and making up of data or results was included, or purposefully put forward conclusions that are not accurate.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—The researcher has a responsibility to uncover, transfer, and exploit knowledge for the benefit of educational institutions. To do so, the researcher takes up the following roles in the course of the study: Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research. The researcher conducts interviews with the participants and guides them in the process. The researcher interprets ideas and responses based on existing literature and related studies and not on the researcher's own knowledge, thoughts, and feelings to avoid the intrusion of bias. Expert in

qualitative methods. The researcher implements the qualitative method correctly. To do so, the researcher assesses himself and seeks help from the research adviser and other research professionals. These help him exhibit competence in explaining the study without biasing the participants, conducting interview properly according to the design, making appropriate field observations, selecting appropriate artifacts, images, and journal portions, employing Environmental Triangulation and Thematic Content Analysis precisely. Collector and Keeper of data. The

researcher ensures different ways of making a record of what is said and done during the interview and Focus Group Discussion, such as taking handwritten notes or audio and video recording. The recordings are transcribed verbatim before data analysis can begin. Records done by the researcher were secured correctly as they contain sensitive information and are relevant to the research. However, the data are being collected, and the researcher's primary responsibility is to safeguard participants and their data. Mechanisms for such safeguarding must be clearly articulated to participants and must be approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research begins. Data analyst. The researcher sees the phenomenon

2.7. Data Collection—To ensure safe educational continuity admits the challenge of COVID-19, this study adhered to the Department of Health (DOH) Administrative Order No. 2020-0015 or the Guidelines on the Risk-Based Public Health Standards for COVID-19 Mitigation, cited by the IATF to aid all sectors in all settings to implement non-pharmaceutical interventions. The following was the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study in the identified school. The researcher would send a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent with Chapters 1 and 2 attached, together with the research instrument explaining the objectives of the study and identifying the participants. The researcher would wait for the response of the SDS before conducting the study. Asking permission from the school heads. After securing the approval of the SDS, the researcher sent letters to the principals of the schools explaining the study to be conducted in their schools. Obtaining consent from the participants. The researcher asked

or problem from the participants' perspective by interpreting data, transcribing and checking, reading between the lines, coding, and theming. The researcher made sure that the findings were true to the participants and that their voices were heard. The researcher organizes and presents data. The researcher presents the problem and the related literature and studies that support it. The study's findings are presented, too, by the research question, stating the results for each one using themes to show how the research questions were answered in the study. Moreover, the researcher gives future directions and implications of the study for improving educational policy and practices.

permission from the participants and their parents/guardians. They were formally oriented about the study and the process they would undergo as participants. Conducting the interview. The researcher conducted the in-depth interview using the interview questionnaire last December 2022. The profile of the participants was taken, notes were jotted down, and conversations were recorded using a sound recorder for ease of transcription. The researcher carefully listened and responded actively during the interviews. The researcher transcribed the interviewees' responses precisely by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. Since the participants used their vernacular language, the researcher translated it into English. Data Coding and Thematic Content Analysis. After the transcription, the data would then be categorized and coded. Then, themes were extracted, and individual data within the participants was compared and contrasted. The researcher then conducted a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needed further explanation and input from the participants; additional information gathered was examined thoroughly and integrated into the existing body

of data. After this, data were compared and contrasted between the participants to develop patterns and trends.

2.8. Data Analysis—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gathered data. The researcher analyzed the answers of the participants from the conducted interviews using Creswell’s Model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2012), themes in qualitative research were similar codes aggregated together to form a major idea in the database. Familiarization with the data was common to all forms of qualitative analysis, the researcher immersed herself in, and became intimately familiar with, their data; reading and re-reading the data and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding was also a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis, involving generating pithy labels for important features of the data relevant to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding was not simply a data reduction method but also an analytic process, so codes capture both a semantic and conceptual reading of the data. The researcher coded every data item and ended this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes was a coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. The researcher ended this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme. Reviewing themes. The researcher reflected on whether the themes tell a convincing and compelling story about the data and began to define the nature of each individual theme and the relationship between the themes. Thematic Content Analysis was employed by the researcher

2.9. Framework of Analysis—The framework analysis of this research was flexible to allow the researcher to either collect all the data

for these. Thematic Content Analysis was a descriptive presentation of qualitative data in which a detailed analysis of each theme was made by identifying the ‘essence’ of each theme and constructing a concise, punchy and informative name for each theme (Andersen, 2013). In addition, to enhance validity and to create a more in-depth picture of the phenomenon, Environmental Triangulation was also employed by the researcher. It was a technique to analyze the results of the same study using different data collection methods. The key was identifying which environmental factors, if any, might influence the information that was received during the study. These environmental factors were changed to see if the findings were the same across the settings (David, 2015). This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations, and other factors such as time, day, and season in which the study occurred. The idea was to determine which of these factors influenced the information received, and these factors were then changed to see if the findings were the same. Validity can be established if the findings remain unaltered under varying environmental factors (Naeem, Saira, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirement, as mentioned, was the use of environmental triangulation best suited to the environment of the research being conducted. Writing up involves weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data and contextualizing it in relation to existing literature.

and then analyze it or do data analysis during the collection process. In the analysis stage, the gathered data was sifted, charted, and sorted

by key issues and themes. This involves a five-step process: (1) familiarization, (2) identifying a thematic framework, (3) indexing, (4) charting, and (5) mapping and interpretation (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Familiarization refers to the process during which the researcher becomes familiarized with the transcripts of the data collected, that was, interview or focus group transcripts, observation, or field notes, and gains an overview of the collected data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). In other words, the researcher becomes immersed in the data by listening to audiotapes, studying the field, or reading the transcripts. Throughout this process, the researcher would become aware of key ideas and recurrent themes and make a note of them. Due to the sheer volume of data that could be collected in qualitative research, the researcher may not be able to review all of the material. Thus, a selection of the data set would be utilized. The selection would depend on several aspects of the data collection process. For example, the mix of methods used (e.g. interviews, documents, observations), The second stage of identifying a thematic framework occurs after familiarization when the researcher recognizes emerging themes or issues in the data set. These emerging themes or issues may have arisen from a priori themes; however, at this stage, the researcher must allow the data to dictate the themes and issues. The researcher uses the notes taken during

the familiarization stage to achieve this. The key issues, concepts, and themes expressed by the participants now form the basis of a thematic framework that can filter and classify the data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Indexing means identifying data portions or sections corresponding to a particular theme. This process is applied to all the textual data that has been gathered (i.e. transcripts of interviews). For the sake of convenience Ritchie and Spencer recommend that a numerical system be used for the indexing references and annotated in the margin beside the text (1994). Qualitative data analysis tools are ideal for such a task. The final stage, mapping and interpretation, involves the analysis of the key characteristics as laid out in the charts. This analysis should be able to provide a schematic diagram of the event/phenomenon thus guiding the researcher in their interpretation of the data set. It was at this point that the researcher was cognizant of the objectives of qualitative analysis, which are: “defining concepts, mapping range and nature of phenomena, creating typologies, finding associations, providing explanations, and developing strategies” (Ritchie and Spencer, 1994:186). Once again, these concepts, technologies, and associations are reflective of the participant. Therefore, any strategy or recommendations made by the researcher echo the true attitudes, beliefs, and values of the participants.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—Trustworthiness was all about establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability. In a qualitative study, trustworthiness was very important because the research study would depend on the result and findings would depend on how the researcher conducts it. The trustworthiness of a research study is important to evaluate its worth. Due to the nature of the qualitative study, honesty in all the data and details was required. Trustworthiness makes the

researcher’s study worthy to read, share, and be proud of. Credibility was how confident the qualitative researcher was in the truth of the research study’s findings. The researcher in this study believed that honesty in everything you do was essential to attain worthwhile success. The researcher has no derogatory records or administrative issues which ruin her integrity. Lincoln and Guba (2000) state that credibility refers to the idea of internal consistency, where the main issue was “how we ensure rigor in the

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

research process and how we communicate to others that we have done so.” Transferability refers to how the qualitative researcher demonstrates that the research study’s findings are applicable to other contexts. In this case, “other contexts” can mean similar situations, similar populations, and similar phenomena. The researcher had already studied the effects of using graphic organizer as strategy in teaching reading comprehension. The use of graphic organizer as a strategy in teaching reading comprehension is effective in the domains analysis and creating. With this, the researcher is interested to know the students’ perspective of using this strategy. Gasson (2004) emphasizes transferability as the extent to which the reader was able to provide generalization of the study based on his own context and could able to address that core issue of “how far a researcher may make claims for a general application of the theory.” Confirmability was the degree of neutrality in the research study’s findings. In other words, this means that the findings are based on participants’ responses and not any potential bias or personal motivations of the researcher. This involves making sure that researcher bias does not skew the interpretation of what the research participants said to fit a certain narrative. The information using the audit trail in this situation is thought-

fully recorded by the researcher which highlights every step of data analysis that was made in order to provide a rationale for the decisions made. This helps establish that the research study’s findings accurately portray participants’ responses. Gasson (2004) states that confirmability was based on the acknowledgement that research is never objective. Dependability was the extent that the study could be repeated by other researchers and that the findings would be consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate your study, they should have enough information from your research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. A qualitative researcher used inquiry audit in order to establish dependability which requires an outside person to review and examine the research process and the data analysis in order to ensure that the findings are consistent and could be repeated. In this component, the use of database was very important in backing up information collected and noting changes for all types of research studies. All the data collected was properly kept for future use as references. Gasson (2004) stated that dependability deals with the core issue that “the way in which a study is conducted should be consistent across time, researchers, and analysis techniques.”

3. Results and Discussion

This part of the research dealt with the research questions and required of this study. The participants disclosed their experiences as property custodian in their respective station during the school year 2022-2023. The school property custodian experiences were also discussed as to how they perform their functions in their respective schools.

3.1. *Experiences of teachers in performing As a school property custodian*—Into Gempes (2018) conducted a study on Teachers with Multiple Ancillary Functions. It describes the experience of teachers from Davao, City. Re-

sults revealed that most participants had positive gains from their experiences, which challenged them to aspire for more self-advancement. Themes were time pressure, heavy workload, stressful and perseverance. Here are some of the participant’s narratives during the interview.

3.1.1. *Time Pressure*—

Time pressure is characterized as the perception of a lack of available time in relation to the amount of workload, which is accompanied with the emotional experience of being rushed (Szollos 2009). This situation can result in a health impairment process as described in the JD-R model (Bakker and Demerouti 2017). Experiencing time pressure over a long time period requires long-term efforts that, in turn, are associated with physiological and/or psychological costs. Over time, these costs result in energy depletion, fatigue and health complaints (Bakker and Demerouti 2007). Indeed, previous research on teachers' perceived time pressure emphasizes negative consequences such as burnout (Skaalvik and Skaalvik 2017). The overwhelming majority of teachers surveyed (92 per cent) said they 'always' or 'frequently' don't have enough time to prepare for effective teaching. The report says this finding holds for all states and territories, primary and secondary schools, all school sectors, and advantaged and disadvantaged schools. Digging deeper into the

3.1.2. Heavy Workload—Workload according to Stickler (2000) is the sum of all activities that take the time of an employee. Workload can at times be heavy (overload or light (under load). Debra (1995) sees role overload as a situation in which employees feel they are being asked to do more than time or ability permits. He further stated that working under time pressure can be stressful because people are anxious when they have a lot to do before some deadline, as time runs out a feeling of impending disaster increases. Teachers' effectiveness is positively influenced by having too much to do or having to tackle too difficult work. Denga and Ekpo (1994) found out that overload whether quantitative or qualitative may lead to stress and concomitant gross ineffectiveness. Orjiji (2000) identified work overload and under load of job as factors that can generate feeling of hopelessness and also may contribute towards

responses to this question – the figure was 86 per cent for teachers with less than two years' experience and 93 per cent for those with more than 10 years (Earp, 2021). Researchers also asked about time for planning. 'A large majority (86 per cent) of teachers said they "always" or "frequently" feel like they do not have sufficient time for high-quality lesson planning,' the report says. 'Again, these results hold across primary and secondary schools, states and territories, school sectors, levels of advantage, and for teachers at all stages of their careers (Earp, 2021). Teachers spoke about the challenges that limit the time they can spend on planning and preparation. According to Earp (2021) that when teachers asked to rate the barriers that were a major issue at their own school, the top three choices were: the workload for what effective teaching entails is too high (86 per cent); not enough personal downtime for teachers to re-charge (78 per cent); and frequent introduction of initiatives by government and school leaders (76 per cent).

lack of motivation, depression and inefficiency. Harbegar and Lohrs (1984) reported that when an executive is stressed up as a result of work overload, becomes moody, emotionally unstable, experiences lowered self-esteem, resentment of supervision, indecision, job dissatisfaction and un productivity. In the research on secondary school teachers' workload in New Zealand, Australian Council For Educational Research ACER (2004) found out that mainly the managers were clearly the group most affected by workload, largely related to their responsibilities. Arnold and Feldman (1986) noted that prioritizing tasks of teachers using support staff for nonprofessional duties, minimizing the number of meetings and using the meeting time for effectively time tabling blocking of time for teachers to meet, filtering the demands of outside agencies, capacity- building, providing teachers with knowledge and skill

they needed to work as competent professionals, lighten workload and increases job satisfaction and work effectiveness.

3.1.3. Stressful—Stress is an unavoidable phenomenon in human life. Stress affects an individual's productivity, effectiveness, personal health and quality of work. Identification of factors causing stress among the teacher educators at work place is very necessary (Jain, Kumar and Kumar 2015). Personal and social characteristics and working conditions may have an effect on teacher's stress level (Saravanan and Muthulakshmi 2017). Under different dimensions of stress, the upper primary school teachers differed significantly with various variables like teaching experience, workload and it is treated as one of the maximum stressors causes stress among teachers (Jahan 2017). Secondary school teachers perceived more stress in all stress factors which are rapport with parent, rapport with the co- worker, workload and lack of resources (Kavita and Hassan 2018). An empirical analysis among teachers working in higher education sector in Kerala explores the nine factors, which significantly influence the organizational stress they are interpersonal relationship in the organization, professional and competence development, recognition in the organization, work environment, autonomy in work, work family interaction, role conflict, job security and remuneration and nonacademic (Jenitta and Mangaleswaran 2016). Teachers have many activities to carry out in the process of executing their main duty of teaching. It is considered as one of the factors responsible for assessing risk level of teachers. Other than this variable like resources, communication level and interpersonal relationship of the teachers in working area are also the factors responsible for assessing stress level of teachers (Islam 2019). The study opined that teacher working in the self-financing institutions are more stressful than teachers working in government institution. The study revealed that self-role distance, work overload, role of ambiguity, role of conflict are the stressful factors among stressful and stress less teachers (Rajarajeswari, 2010). Stress not only affects the physical and psychological state but also had an adverse impact on family and social life of the teacher (Goswani 2018). Stress is not always negative. It results in eustress and distress. Eustress helps in restoring our energy and distress normally has a negative impact on our performance (Sharma 2018). The work related stress emerges due to a pattern of emotional, cognitive, behavioral and physiological reactions to adverse and noxious aspects of work content, work organization and work environment (Narban Narban, 2016). Each profession has its own work related stress. Teaching as a profession is no more the profession of a little stress (Parray et. al., 2016). Teacher's experiences stress due to hazardous working conditions, a lack of materials and lack of output from the administration (Alson 2009). Teachers stress is a reaction of teachers to the unwanted environment factors. The stress level of teachers negatively affects the performance level of the teachers by lowering their productivity as well as it affects the performance level of the educational institution (Khan et. al., 2012). Majority of teachers perceived their work related stress due to dependent variables like gender, education, family income and economic instability (Parashar et. al., 2009). Job insecurity, poor student's behavior, ineffective leadership at departmental levels results in stress level of teachers and it also results in psychological distress among teachers (Sibgh Rani, 2015). Educational status and years of experience of teachers are the factors responsible for creating stress among teachers (Solomon et. al., 2017). The study made in Secondary schools in Esan Central Senatorial District, Edo, State Nigeria observed that the teachers face risk due to work

overload, crowded class conditions, poor working conditions, lack of social support and lack of accessories. Stress lessens teachers' quality of instructional delivery, lowers teacher's morale, job satisfaction, job performance and increases attrition (Kamboj, 2017). The study opined that the stress associated to student's disruptive behavior and to difficulties perceived by teachers in managing conflicts has a greater incidence of female teachers, on second cycle teachers and

on intermediate stages in the profession (Santiago, et. al.,2018). The study investigates about the highest levels of perceived teacher's work related stress were caused by changes in terms and conditions, without consultation given responsibility, without the authority to take decisions; while in the category support, the same was true for stress factors lack of funds of resources to do the job and limited or no access to training (Agai-Demjaha, et. al.,2015).

3.1.4. Perseverance—The National Research Council considers perseverance an indicator of work ethic and has identified it as an important 21st-century intrapersonal skill (Pellegriano Hilton, 2013). Teachers who promote perseverance among their students can foster engagement and produce excellent results in the classroom. Perseverance of teachers is tested when they have worked hard but are not recognized and compensated in return, worked extra mile and experienced sleepless nights in preparing reports, forgot to wear lipstick and comb their hair, got tired and frustrated, burnt midnight candles to submit reports, felt pressured and anxious that they might not meet high expectations, and had the feeling that the brain is splitting minding one function over another. The data were supported by the study of Pearson et al. (1994), who revealed that teachers

who were empowered in their respective stations were already walking the extra mile to accomplish the assigned functions. However, they were not compensated in return. It was further revealed in the study entitled 'Relationships and Resilience: A Role for School Principal' that when teachers encounter difficult experiences, it is only because they are tired and lack energy due to multiple workloads or ancillary functions (Peters Pearce, 2012). In like manner, (Cannon, 1996) cited that in countries such as China and Japan, hard work and perseverance contribute toward academic achievement. This is an important factor of what everybody needs to develop in whatever organization you are in. Here are some of the testimonies of the participants of the study Figure 3 shows teachers' experiences as school property custodians and the emergence of the four themes: time pressure, heavy workload, stressful and perseverance.

3.2. Coping mechanisms of the teachers as they perform as school property custodian—According to data in many parts of the world, teachers take extra time to do their ancillary functions. For instance, due to the ancillary function, the Department of Education committed itself to conducting regular large-scale research on teacher ancillary works in English

schools. Data from 2018 shows that participants reported high levels of ancillary work, which they believed to be manageable only if they were working through long hours (Wiggins, 2015). Furthermore, here are some of the mechanisms used by some of the Prosperidad district's teachers to perform as school property custodians.

3.2.1. Motivating One Another—

Fig. 3. The emerging themes on the experiences of the teachers' in performing as school property custodian

Motivating one another emerged as a coping mechanism of teachers with ancillary functions because teachers are counting support and reassurance from their Heads, colleagues, and friends, and love and encouragement from family and friends. It adheres to the contentions of (Baker, 2006) when he reiterated that individuals who establish open communication with other people are also well-loved and accepted; thus, they are more satisfied and less troubled in their work. It is considered to establish a positive relationship and encourage resilience in one's life, thus greater adaptability to cope with life's difficult experiences. More so, attachment style is a determining factor in the cognition of social support, which is directly related to coping. He added that a strong support system would also result into a positive relationship with other people and would feel satisfaction with the amount of support they receive. These reports are consistent with the study of Repak (2009), who reported that faculty involvement and support were the important ingredients in academic success of a teacher guided by their immediate superior. It enhances their sense of well-being and belonging in the educational community. It brings both personal and emotional varying degrees of support to combat such difficulties. In the same way, Castallo (1992) also cited that to prevent outcomes of excessive stress because of multiple ancillary functions, school heads need to be visionary and encourage teachers in managing their multiple ancillary functions, while foster teamwork and sense of ownership within the school community. Furthermore, another experience was accentuated by the view of (Schwab, 1983) which tells that teacher who are contented with decisions and the support system provided by school heads have a more optimistic approach towards teaching and learning. Hence, this notion was also supported by (Coombe, 2008; Don et al., 2016), stating that schools have greater accountability of providing teachers with enough resources with clear position descriptions by setting goals and objectives in their profession to eliminate conflict and ambiguity, in order to establish open collaboration as motivation. When teachers see their work is relevant and meaningful, when they feel they have ownership, and when the work has value, they are more likely to be motivated. According to Impact Teachers, a website devoted to creating outstanding schools, "A motivated teacher is crucial to a successful classroom. They will look at teaching through a different lens and, in doing so, motivate their students in their learning, too. Motivation helps to energize, direct, and sustain positive behavior over a long period. It involves working toward goals and tailoring activities to achieve this purpose. It also helps to drive creativity and curiosity, sparking the desire needed for students to want to learn more." Motivating teachers leads to motivated and more successful students. With teacher motivation driven by a combination of intrinsic and extrinsic factors, finding the proper incentives to influence them is complex and multifaceted (Crehan, 2016; Martin, 2018). While many systems have experimented with motivating teachers through bonus pay for meeting specific targets, results have been mixed for such direct extrinsic motivation (Crehan, 2016; Education Commission, 2019; World Bank, 2018). Instead, research shows that allowing teachers more agency to work towards different promotion opportunities can offer a strong incentive to remain in the profession (Cabus, Haelermans, and Flink, 2020; Calvert, 2016; Cordingley et al., 2019; Tournier et al., 2019). Measures that improve teachers' professionalism, such as collaboration and continuous professional development, have also improved motivation (Cordingley et al., 2019; Education Commission, 2019; Tournier et al., 2019). School leaders can play a vital role in inspiring teachers by offering support, consistent standards, and effective evaluation and accountability structures. Such support from school leaders can further improve pro-

fessionalism and reduce rates of teacher absenteeism (Education Commission, 2019; Martin, 2018; TTF, 2016).

3.2.2. Optimism and positivity—Optimism and positivity become visible because teachers consider their ancillary function as an opportunity and not as a multitude of tasks; they ignore criticism that may come their way and take positive thoughts in order to generate positive ideas. It was mentioned by Calisee that if you do not want to have additional stress in life, be optimistic all the time because you will be inspired to do better with your job and yield positive results. The case of Calisee articulates the view of (Bonanno Keltner, 1997), who emphasized that positive emotions and continuing contact with supportive people can help reduce stress in the person's social environment. This is supported by (Fredrickson, Tugade, Waugh, Larkin, 2003) when they said that ongoing positivism will lead to building up a range of holistic personal resources that are lasting coping mechanisms and habitual personal resources. One important role in achieving something is atti-

3.2.3. Having life-work balance—Achieving life-work balance because they conditioned their mind to be healthy by taking food supplement, eating at the right time, hanging out with friends once in a while, setting aside time for family, and even finding time to meditate, pray, and offer to God everything that they have encountered. These reports are consistent with a study by (Rife Hall, 2015); they emphasized that a person who knows how to balance their work, family, and life commitments is happier in his jobs and is more likely to stay and work towards a rewarding and prolific job. This is also in consonance with the statement mentioned by Halpern and Murphy (2013); they said that employees differ in their strategies in balancing work from other domains. Some prefer to

tude. When a person fails at one point in his life, people would say that that person probably has a negative attitude toward things. In school, the attitude of the students toward certain subjects often reflects on their performance. The teachers often state that laziness, for example, a negative attitude, is directly proportional to the students' failure rate (A. Yahaya, J. Ramli, and Y. Boon, 2009). On the other hand, a positive attitude towards the subjects would encourage a person to learn the content much better. According to Zulkarnain, Saim, and Abd Talib (2011), students' attitudes must be nurtured throughout the teaching and learning process to have a good and positive result. Students' ability to apply the knowledge and learning they gained is a positive result of effective teaching and learning processes. A positive attitude can motivate a student's active participation, critical thinking, improved interaction, and communication skills.

set limits between work and non-work-related functions, referred to as "segmenting". It is a situation in which employees are capable of giving the right amount of time and effort to their work as well as their personal life outside the work. Work-life balance is normally said to be achieved when an individual's right to a fulfilled life inside and outside the paid work is accepted and respected. Some people may refer to the flexible working arrangements that allow both parents and non-parents to avail of working arrangements that provide a balance between work responsibilities and personal responsibilities (Marafi, 2012). It leads to the harmonious and holistic integration of work, family, social life, and personal life and is the extent to which individuals are equally involved

in and equally satisfied with their professional role and their family role. Work-life balance is vital to teacher effectiveness and satisfaction in the context of student learning. Research has proved that a good work-life balance results in the faculty's wellness and improves student behavior. Moreover, a good work-life balance gives job satisfaction and helps achieve higher retention rates in the institution (Lakshmi Kumar 2011). Over the course of their career, every teacher faces some difficulties in attaining a balance between professional and personal life due to a lack of clear boundaries between work and life because of the flexibility of schedules. Moreover, during the previous decades, the work pressures in academia have been constant nationally and globally, thereby creating many stressors. It has been argued that rising stressors in academia are 'eroding' the operating capabilities of universities (Perry, et al., 1997). Very few studies have examined academics' ability to balance work and personal life and overcome work-life conflicts (Bell, Ra-

jendran Theiler (2012). Zedeck (1992) hypothesized that high levels of perceived job pressure stress and job threat stress would predict increased levels of work-life conflict, and decreased levels of work-life balance. However, Punia Khosla (2009) found that in the education sector, collaboration strategy is used in the majority dimensions of organizational role stress, which signifies that in this sector, people wish to remain conflict and stress-free as it is directly linked with the teacher performance in and outside the classroom which are part and parcel of their organizational environment. Miryala Nagapriya (2012) highlighted the necessity of adopting work-life balance policies for teachers teaching at different levels. Based upon the different elements especially about government and private institution teachers, the study proposed a proper policy for work life balance. Since Quality of work-life has direct correlates with cost incurred on employees whether by inflow or outflow. When employees.

3.2.4. Good planning and time management—Good planning and time management is the first major factors that help the teachers in performing ancillary functions. For a teacher with ancillary functions, "first things first" so that things would slow smoothly. In order for them not to forget the task for the day, they prepared checklist of things to do, placed reminder, made plan of activities ahead of time or did things in advance based on urgency and importance. This was supported by (Abban, 2011) when he stressed that the time you have wasted never comes back. It plays a significant role in one's life. A person who knows how to manage his time would not find any difficulty in the performance of his job and are labeled as successful employees of the school. He further regarded time management as the one which is connected with person's tools, skills, and activities in order

to work efficiently every day. It is analogous to the word 'systematic' which in itself is a very positive trait to be possessed by an effective individual. Working as a teacher requires excellent time management skills. Teachers need to balance the long-term goals of the classroom, the immediate educational needs of the students and the large volume of paperwork that comes with every assignment. Between writing lesson plans, grading exams, and actually teaching, teachers often feel that it is impossible to fit everything into the allotted time frame. Although the career path seems to have too much work for the number of hours in a day, it is possible to manage the situation and clear extra time in the classroom and outside of class. With effective time management skills, teachers can increase their productivity and provide a better education for their students. Teacher time management

must start with setting priorities and organizing the day around the most important tasks. Setting priorities can help keep teachers on track throughout the day, even when the unexpected occurs, and the workload can seem overwhelming. Effective prioritizing is about arranging workload based on both the importance of the tasks as well the resulting impact of the completed tasks. Teachers must be able to assess whether projects can be put on hold if the outcomes are not as impactful as others. The participants or Custodians 1-4 narrated how Good planning and time management work for them in performing their responsibilities and making work for them manageable. Bearing the accountable officers' obligation to carry out their responsibility to safe-keep properties in conformity with the law and be answerable for their

decisions and activities relating to properties under their custody shall only be extinguished upon return/turnover of the. This task or job was very challenging. In the same manner, articles by Gempes (2016) also cite that proper time management plays a vital role in motivating employees and, thus, improving the organization's performance. In addition to that, an important part of planning is prioritizing. When you prioritize tasks, you spend most of the time on the most urgent ones and prioritize them (Tavakoli, Tavakoli, Pouresmaeil, 2013). Figure 4 shows teachers' Coping mechanisms for the challenges of performing as school property custodians and the emergence of the four themes: Motivating one another, Optimism and positivity, Having a life and work balance, and Good planning and time management.

3.3. Educational management Insights gained from the experiences of the informants— Educational insights play a very significant role in qualitative research. This part of the study

will briefly describe how the participants view the cited issues at hand. Some of the participants' revelations and contemplations were as follows:

*3.3.1. Keep an optimistic attitude—*The participants were very enthusiastic when they claimed they had to stay optimistic about their current predicaments. They were all aware that there were some ancillary functions to handle that the school needed to be fully operational. As attested by Post, Jennifer (2019) said that when something is going wrong, the first thing people usually say is to "stay strong" and "stay positive." Those little affirmations sometimes work, and it is important to remember that words can go a long way during a time of negativity, especially in the workplace. She further said "Having a positive attitude in the workplace will not necessarily make you better at your job,

but it will improve the way people view you as a person, so they may be more inclined to help you succeed and cheer you on". Maintaining a positive attitude at work will benefit your career and steer you towards a promotion. 36 per cent of professionals polled on LinkedIn agree that a positive attitude is the most important quality that employers look for in candidates and team members. However, maintaining a positive attitude on a daily basis in the workplace is harder than you may think. Work is stressful and challenging, and most professionals face deadlines and obstacles on a weekly (if not daily) basis. This is not an environment that fosters a positive attitude – you really have to work at it (Resume Target, 2020).

3.3.2. Being Flexible—

Fig. 4. The emerging themes on the coping mechanisms of the teachers on the challenges in performing as school property custodians

Berwick (2020) stated that being flexible is an asset that a teachers need to possess. Teachers responsibility require to adjust in the curriculum and does some additional functions, it's important to maintain that flexibility in order to accomplished all the tasked. Along those lines, teachers can rethink the idea of deadlines when accepting work in order to meet their students' needs in the class. Seeing the human in the student helps to relieve stress associated with deadlines and lets students create products of their own learning without fear of repercussions. Flexibility isn't easy to implement at first. It's a complete mind-shift for teachers and students. First, is to establish relationships with the students based on respect, and in order to maintain this relationship, they turn in their work. Flexible deadlines also work for me because my classroom is based on choice. I find

that students are more motivated to complete assignments because they can choose what they learn and how they produce the evidence of their learning (Arvisais, 2020). Teachers can also show flexibility by creating innovative ways to accomplished the required report as a property custodian through digital applications. In like manner, consistent and authentic digital technology integration in classes helps students ease back into a face-to-face environment and prepares them for the future. We've seen a noticeable shift in society to daily reliance on technology. Whether it's communicating through email, presentations, or videoconferencing for meetings, students and teachers will need to be adept in maneuvering technology. Creating opportunities to use technology in the classroom helps students practice using digital tools (Charland, 2020).

3.3.3. *Consider your health*—The participants shared that no matter how busy one is in work and in professional studies, it is very important to consider one's health, especially this time. Because teaching is such an intensive job, educators can greatly benefit from learning about practicing health and self-care. Unfortunately, teachers may worry that taking care of themselves can lead to self-absorption and distract them from their students. However, despite the misleading title, self-care isn't at all about selfishness. For the participants, practicing self-care can be in the best interest of everyone in the school. Self-care is all about taking care of one's health and making sure that they have everything they need to thrive as a teacher. Without taking care of one self, they won't have the energy to help their students. The participants further explained that self-care is an important component of a teacher's mental health, but they deemed that there are misconceptions about what it is. It's common for educators to dismiss the self-care movement as

selfish or superficial. But for them, self-care is so much more than breakfast in bed or treating oneself to a spa day. It's about taking care of their health so that they are prepared to be the best teacher they can be for themselves and for their students. The importance and benefits of self-care extend to every profession, but within some careers, it is more stigmatized than in others. People in caregiving positions like teachers, for example, often find it easier to tell others to take care of their health than to do so themselves. Because educators are encouraged to focus so much energy on others and so little on themselves, self-care is necessary for teachers to maintain good mental health (Waterford, 2021). When left unchecked, teacher stress can lead to burnout and contribute to the high turnover rate in education. But self-care can turn this around and help keep teachers from getting burned out. This means that self-care isn't just a good personal habit, but it's in your students' and colleagues' best interest, too. By eating well, sleeping enough, exercising, and

finding other ways to take care of yourself, self-care can help you reach your potential in the classroom, which will in turn help your students succeed (Waterford, 2021).

3.3.4. *Commitment and dedication—C*

Commitment and dedication are the first major themes that emerged because they learn to embrace whatever task is assigned to them, stay focused on the task, work with commitment and dedication, and know how to balance time and carry out the task with flying colors. It affirms the assumption of (Meyer Parfyonova, 2010) that employees' commitment to an organization is a very important indicator for an employee to stay, thus attending regularly and performing his job effectively. Dedication is characterized by enthusiasm, inspiration, pride, and challenge. Additional inputs for our discussion came from the participants' narratives. In the words of their participants or property custodians, they have increasingly become critical actors in school systems. Their responsibilities have been extended, and they face growing complexity and demands for safety and availability of the property when the teachers and

students need it. Moreover, it was articulated that a strong commitment gives employees a sense of accomplishment in their jobs, shielding them from the negative effects of stressors (Kobasa, 1982). The opposing point of view is that a greater commitment increases employees' exposure to the harmful effects of stressors. In like manner, teachers who have greater opportunities to encounter ancillary responsibilities in the collective decision-making feel a stronger commitment to the overall organization fulfilled by the work they do, opposing the feeling that they are under-appreciated and overworked for little positive gain (Castallo, 1992). Figure 5 shows educational management insights gained from the informants' experiences and the emergence of the four themes: Keeping a Positive Attitude, Being Flexible, Health Consideration, and Commitment and dedication.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presented the study summary. The findings were summarized, and the implications and future directions were drawn. My study's purpose was to solicit the experiences of the school property custodian of Prosperidad District Agusan del Sur. To achieve the research objectives, a qualitative phenomenological method was utilized with thematic analysis. In adherence to Cresswell's (2006) guidelines, open-ended interview questions were applied to get an authentic understanding of people's experiences. Furthermore, this interview approach encouraged participants to present their own definition or meaning of the phenomenon being explored.

4.1. *Findings*—The study's findings on the experiences of the school property custodian revealed that they were indeed subject to time pressure, a heavy workload, stress, and perseverance. It was revealed that the school property custodians' coping mechanisms include moti-

vating one another, optimism and positivity, having a life-work balance, and good planning. As to the educational management insights gained from the participants, school property custodian felt that they needed to keep an optimistic attitude, being flexible, consider your health and commitment and dedication.

Fig. 5. Educational management insights gained from the Experiences of the informants

4.2. *Implications*—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. Based on the experiences of the school property custodian, the results of the interview revealed the following themes: First, time pressure to be assigned as property custodian is time pressure considering the bulk of paperwork and reports to be submitted every month. Second, heavy workload, aside from the primary function, which is to teach in the classroom it added to the workload of the teacher. Third, I was stressed in preparing the reports concerning the school property and equipment at hand. Fourth was perseverance; in order for the school to comply with the required reports on property and equipment, the school property custodian needed to persevere and do what it took to satisfy the needed reports for submission. On the coping mechanisms of the school property custodian, one of the themes was motivating one another. The custodian knows that support is needed to accomplish the enormous task assigned. Co-teachers play an important role in motivating the property custodian to perform well in the assigned task. The second theme identified from the property custodian coping mechanisms was to have optimism and positivity despite all the difficulty encountered in being a caretaker of the school and the property, both the record and the actual thing. The third theme identified was having a life-work balance. With all the hardships encountered in preparing the report, the custodian needs to

4.3. *Future Directions*—Based on the study's findings, it was important that some important moves were taken into consideration and made available for the school property custodian, considering the bulk of paperwork on their assigned function. This study may provide an avenue to enlighten the school heads to continue supporting their respective property custodians in assigning teaching loads. The school

have some time for personal relaxation to distress and recharge. The last theme identified was to have good planning and time management. The combination of ancillary work added to the actual teaching loads needs to have good planning and time management as both are considered important in the school's functioning. The educational management insights gained from the school property custodian identified the first theme as keeping an optimistic attitude. Despite all the hardship and difficulty of being a custodian of the school property, they keep in mind that someday, somehow, all things would be out of place and can be done in a split second. The second theme identified by the school property custodian was being flexible. In our daily activities, new things come along the way. Let us be flexible and ready to gamble in order to accomplish the task of being the custodian of the school property. The third theme was to consider our health. We should be able to know our body's limitations and our health and well-being. We should do some self-care; after all, our capital was our human body. If not given some importance, it would become our problem and a possible cause of not reaching our retirement age. The fourth theme identified by the property custodian was the commitment and dedication of our teachers who are assigned as property custodians. There is no denying that the property custodians were really committed and dedicated to doing their tasks despite the difficulties encountered.

heads may help the custodians account for the property and equipment in a practical and systematic way in the years to come. The school property custodian may continue to encourage property custodians to do their assigned tasks. Despite the limited technology resources in the inventory and accounting of school property, they should encourage all possible partners to inventory electronically. Teachers, learners, and

parents should consider their possible contributions to protecting school property and equipment from abuse and damaging action. Similar studies may be conducted in other regions or divisions for future researchers. The researchers may consider other aspects of the school property custodian's experiences.

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